

Sample ID **3-6 (Combined)**

Operator ID **user**

Notes

Elapsed Time	00:01:00
Median Diam.	124.2 nm
Mean Diam.	136.7 nm
Polydispersity	0.210
GSD	1.548

Lognormal Size Distribution

d(nm)	G(d)	C(d)	d(nm)	G(d)	C(d)	d(nm)	G(d)	C(d)
60.6	26	5	111.2	97	40	166.8	80	75
71.0	44	10	117.6	99	45	179.5	70	80
79.0	58	15	124.2	100	50	195.4	58	85
86.0	70	20	131.3	99	55	217.5	44	90
92.6	80	25	138.8	97	60	254.9	26	95
98.8	87	30	147.0	93	65			
105.0	93	35	156.2	87	70			